

EFFECT OF EXPOSURE
TO
ENVIRONMENTAL
TOBACCO SMOKE
ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Tobacco is a product prepared from the leaves of the tobacco plant by curing them. The plant is part of the genus *Nicotiana* and of the Solanaceae (nightshade) family. While more than 70 species of tobacco are known, the chief commercial crop is *N. tabacum*. The more potent variant *N. rustica* is also used around the world. Tobacco contains the alkaloid nicotine, which is a stimulant. Dried tobacco leaves are mainly used for smoking in cigarettes, cigars, pipe tobacco, and flavored shisha tobacco. They can be also consumed as snuff, chewing tobacco, and dipping tobacco. Burning tobacco is the main source of indoor pollution in the developed world. Tobacco smoke contains about 4,000 chemicals including carcinogens, irritants and toxic gases. Nicotine, benzene and benzo(a)pyrene. The gas phase includes carbon monoxide, ammonia, dimethylnitrosamine, formaldehyde, hydrogen cyanide and acrolein. Methyl bromide, an ozone-depleting chemical commonly used to fumigate the soil prior planting tobacco seedlings. Tobacco growers are susceptible to an occupational illness known as green tobacco sickness.

Tobacco is the fourth most common risk factor for disease worldwide. The economic costs of tobacco use are equally devastating. In addition to the high public health costs of treating tobacco-caused diseases, tobacco kills people at the height of their productivity, depriving families of breadwinners and nations of a healthy workforce. Tobacco users are also less productive while they are alive due to increased sickness. A 1994 report estimated that the use of tobacco resulted in an annual global net loss of US\$ 200 thousand million, a third of this loss being in developing countries. Tobacco and poverty are inextricably linked. Many studies have shown that in the poorest households in some low-income countries as much as 10% of total household expenditure is on tobacco. This means that these families have less money to spend on basic items such as food, education and health care. In addition to its direct health effects, tobacco leads to malnutrition, increased health care costs and premature death.

Tobacco smoke contains over 4000 chemicals in the form of particles and gases.

Many potentially toxic gases are present in higher concentrations in sidestream smoke than in mainstream smoke and nearly 85% of the smoke in a room results from sidestream smoke.

The particulate phase includes tar (itself composed of many chemicals), nicotine, benzene and benzo(a)pyrene. The gas phase includes carbon monoxide, ammonia, dimethylnitrosamine, formaldehyde, hydrogen cyanide and acrolein. Some of these have marked irritant properties and some 60 are known or suspected carcinogens (cancer causing substances). The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in the USA has classified environmental tobacco smoke as a class A (known human) carcinogen along with asbestos, arsenic, benzene and radon gas [Lee Jong-wook, WHO 2004]

The WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control, which was adopted in May 2003 by WHO's 192 member States, is intended as a common framework in which countries can work together to address the challenge that tobacco use represents at the global level. In the year 2004 the Central Govt of India passed a legislation on advertisement, production, trade and sale of tobacco and tobacco products .banning the advertisement of tobacco & tobacco products on tv, newspapers and media from 01 may 2004 Reason tobacco leaves contain an alkaloid nicotine which is lethal carcinogen and causes addiction.

Table 2 TOXIC LEVELS OF NICOTINE

A] Minimum Lethal Dose of Nicotine

Adult Human 40 mg ~0.5- 1.0 mg/kg ;

- Topically Child 4mg /kg , Adult 65mg
- Human 0.36mg/kg
- Cow [1- 1 ½ year old Bulls & Heifer] > 1 gm
- Horse & Cow 200-400 mg
- Sheep 100-200 mg
- 18 month Lambs 200-300 mg
- Cat & Dog 20-100 mg
- Mouse 40 mg

Identification of nicotine in tobacco leaves
GEOL .LA 400 ST NMR spectroscophotometer
was used for Nuclear magnetic resonance
spectroscopy . Tobacco Samples were
collected from various Tobacco factories in
Kanpur UP India .

According to the NMR spectrum of nicotine
molecule [Bhacco N.S 1962-63] NMR
spectrum of tobacco leaves of Tobacco Seed
variety PP, KP, BB , AG , RB respectively .
When compared with show identical peaks in
7.5-7.0 ppm and 2.5 – 1.0 ppm region
confirming the presence of nicotine in these
leaf samples .

This technique was later utilized to identify
nicotine in commercial tobacco [Table 4]

TABLE 4 VARIOUS BRANDS OF CHEWING TOBACCO
MANUFACTURED IN INDIA [0.3-0.5 mg / gm NICOTINE
CONTENT]

MAHARASTRA

- . [A3] OM SPECIAL
- [B3] HATHI CHAP

UTTAR PRADESH

- [A1] MOHINI
- [B1] SWAGAT
- [C1] SHRIRAM
- [C2] GHAI CHAP
- [C6] GANESH
- [B6] UDTA PANCHI
- [B7] HIRAN CHAP
- [B8] MEHAK
- [B9] TULSI
- [C5] MADHU

• TABLE 5 VARIOUS BRANDS OF CHEWING
TOBACCO MANUFACTURED IN INDIA

[0.3-0.5 mg / gm NICOTINE CONTENT]

JHARKHAND

[A4] RAJA CHAP

[C4] KUBER TOBACCO

[B4] MIRAJ TOBACCO

CHATISGARH

[A3] TOTA CHAP

[C3] MAHARAJA CHAP

[B5] BHARAT CHAP TEJ TOBACCO

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Many potentially toxic gases are present in higher concentrations in sidestream smoke than in mainstream smoke and nearly 85% of the smoke in a room results from sidestream smoke.

The particulate phase includes tar (itself composed of many chemicals), nicotine, benzene and benzo(a)pyrene. The gas phase includes carbon monoxide, ammonia, dimethylnitrosamine, formaldehyde, hydrogen cyanide and acrolein. Some of these have marked irritant properties and some 60 are known or suspected carcinogens (cancer causing substances). The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in the USA has classified environmental tobacco smoke as a class A (known human) carcinogen along with asbestos, arsenic, benzene and radon gas [Lee Jong-wook, WHO 2004]

A] INDOOR AIR POLLUTION LEVELS OF NICOTINE

- Billiard parlour 19.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
- Home 12.1- 14.4
- Departmental store 0.6
- Automobile 0.4

B] INDOOR AIR QUALITY Nicotine $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

- Restaurants 0.5- 37 average 5.4
- 7.1 -37 average 15
- Offices 3- 48
- 9-32
- 6-20 average 5
- Public common areas 2-36
- 1-3
- Smoking sections of airplanes 6-29 average 15
- 0-112 average 9
- Non smoking sections of airplanes 0-40 average 6
- Food counters of shopping malls 1.6- 3.1 average 2.3

Nicotine is the primary chemical responsible for smoking addiction. Nicotine stimulates the production of dopamine in the nucleus accumbens, the brain's "pleasure centre" dopamine and norepinephrine – neurotransmitters within the regions of the brain responsible for feelings of pleasure, which causes a sudden release of glucose. Stimulation is followed by depression and fatigue leading the abuser to seek more nicotine. Addiction to nicotine results in withdrawal symptoms when a chronic smoker tries to stop smoking for 24 hours they had increased anger, hostility and aggression and loss of social cooperation, take longer to regain emotional equilibrium following stress. [NIDA FACTS 2006]

TABLE 3 CIGARETTE

INGREDIENTS

-Acetone [Nail Polish Remover]	Hydrogen Cyanide [Gas Chamber Poison]
Acetic Acid [Vinegar]	Methane [Swamp Gas]
Ammonia [Floor/Toilet Cleaner]	Methanol [Rocket Fuel]
Arsenic [Poison]	Naphthalene [Mothballs]
Butane [Cigarette Lighter Fluid]	Nicotine [Insecticide/ Addictive Drug]
Cadmium [Rechargeable Battery]	Nitrobenzene [Gasoline Additive]
Carbon Monoxide [Car Exhaust]	Nitrous Oxide Phenols [Disinfectant]
DDT/ Dieldrin [Insecticides]	Stearic Acid [Candle Wax]
Ethanol [Alcohol]	Toluene Industrial Solvent]
Formaldehyde [Preservative - Body Tissue & Fabric]	Vinyl Chloride [Makes PVC2]
Hexamine [Barbecue Lighter]	

Tobacco is a risk factor for oral cancer, oral cancer recurrence, adult periodontal diseases and congenital defects such as cleft lip and palate in children. Tobacco suppresses the immune system's response to oral infection, compromises healing following oral surgical and accidental wounding, promotes periodontal degeneration in diabetics and adversely affects the cardiovascular system.

Carcinogens in cigar smoke

benzene , aromatic amines (especially carcinogens such as 2-naphthylamine and 4-aminobiphenyl) ,
vinyl chloride ,
ethylene oxide,arsenic ,chromium ,cadmium
,nitrosamines ,polynuclear , aromatic hydrocarbons

Cigar smoking linked to death from cancer of the pancreas and bladder.

NIDA FACTS 2006

Smoking tobacco causes heart disease arteries become hardened and tend to shrink , causing an heart attack.

nicotine causes thickening of blood.
Nicotine increases chlorestrol deposistion.

According to Prof David Busher Hayas [Dublin.Ireland]

EFFECT OF PASSIVE SMOKING ON THE HUMAN BODY

Some of the immediate effects of passive smoking include eye irritation, headache, cough, sore throat, dizziness and nausea. Adults with asthma can experience a significant decline in lung function when exposed, while new cases of asthma may be induced in children whose parents smoke. Short term exposure to tobacco smoke also has a measurable effect on the heart in non-smokers. Just 30 minutes exposure is enough to reduce coronary blood flow.

In the longer term, passive smokers suffer an increased risk of a range of smoking-related diseases. Non-smokers who are exposed to passive smoking in the home, have a 25 per cent increased risk of heart disease and lung cancer. Scientific Committee on Tobacco and Health (SCOTH) concluded that passive smoking is a cause of lung cancer and ischaemic heart disease in adult non-smokers, and a cause of respiratory disease, cot death, middle ear disease and asthmatic attacks in children. A more recent review of the health impacts of passive smoking by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) noted that “the evidence is sufficient to conclude that involuntary smoking is a cause of lung cancer in never smokers”.

UNCTAD 2004

The British Medical Association has conservatively estimated that secondhand smoke causes at least 1,000 deaths a year in the UK.

RISK TO YOUNG CHILDREN

Almost half of all children in the UK are exposed to tobacco smoke at home. Passive smoking increases the risk of lower respiratory tract infections such as bronchitis, pneumonia and bronchiolitis in children. One study found that in households where both parents smoke, young children have a 72 per cent increased risk of respiratory illnesses. Passive smoking causes a reduction in lung function and increased severity in the symptoms of asthma in children, and is a risk factor for new cases of asthma in children. Passive smoking is also associated with middle ear infection in children as well as possible cardiovascular impairment and behavioural problems.

Mothers Smoking - 20 cigarettes

Babies receive 9.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{day}$ Nicotine

Breast milk ~ 200-500 ppb

Scientists from Canada reported finding evidence of cigarette smoke in fetal hair, the first biochemical proof that the offspring of non-smoking mothers can be affected by passive cigarette smoke. Smoking during pregnancy can harm the baby [1994-02-22]

Tobacco causes impotency in men in a study by Dr. Klaus Anderson Copenhagen, Denmark there is a rise in impotency in men with a nicotine addiction .women with smoking husbands are unable to conceive .number of still births are more in cases of smoking fathers . Exposure to passive smoking during pregnancy is an independent risk factor for low birth weight. A recent study has also shown that babies exposed to their mother's tobacco smoke before they are born grow up with reduced lung function

Parental smoking is also a risk factor for sudden infant death syndrome (cot death).

GREEN TOBACCO SICKNESS

Tobacco growers are susceptible to an occupational illness known as green tobacco sickness. This is caused by the absorption of nicotine through the skin from contact with wet tobacco leaves. Symptoms of GTS include nausea, weakness, dizziness and abdominal cramps, and fluctuations in blood pressure and heart rates. It is not known exactly how many tobacco workers are affected by green tobacco sickness. Among the pesticides commonly used are aldicarb and chlorpyrifos, both highly toxic substances. Methyl bromide, an ozone-depleting chemical, is also commonly used to fumigate the soil prior to planting tobacco seedlings.. These chemicals leach into the soil and find their way into streams, rivers, and food chains. These substances may indirectly cause the genetic selection of pesticide-resistant mosquitoes or flies, making the control of diseases such as malaria difficult.

Breathing other people's smoke is called passive, involuntary or secondhand smoking. The non-smoker breathes "sidestream" smoke from the burning tip of the cigarette and "mainstream" smoke that has been inhaled and then exhaled by the smoker. Secondhand smoke (SHS) is a major source of indoor air pollution.

The American Cancer Society estimates that cigarettes are responsible for about 431,000 Lung cancer deaths in the United States . The National Cancer Center (NCC) South Korea officially confirmed that smoking causes lung cancer [2002-04-11]

A study published in the British Medical Journal the effects of passive smoking on the risk of heart disease may have been under-estimated. The researchers found that blood cotinine levels among non-smokers were associated with a 50-60% increased risk of heart disease. For those who do not inhale, tobacco smoke does not reach the lungs in the same quantity as it does in cigarette smokers. Therefore, the risk of death from lung cancer is not as high as it is for cigarette smokers, but is still several times higher than the risk for non-smokers.

Squamous and small cell carcinomas, arising from the larger bronchi, are traditionally associated with smoking, but relative and absolute increases in the incidence of adenocarcinomas of the lung have been increasingly recognised. A recent study from Switzerland demonstrates rising incidence rates for adenocarcinomas in both younger men and women in the early 1990s, the rates being more than 3-fold higher than for squamous carcinomas in the same groups. This alteration in histological pattern almost certainly reflects changes in the pattern of exposure of bronchial tissues to tobacco-associated carcinogens. Smokers of modern low-tar filtered cigarettes tend to compensate by increasing the number and depth of puffs, the peripheral parts of the lung are thus more exposed to larger amounts of tobacco-associated carcinogens, and it is in the peripheral parts of the lung that adenocarcinomas develop. The diagnostic and therapeutic implications of an increase in lung adenocarcinomas are likely Nicotine is the substance in tobacco that causes addiction

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The WHO Oral Health Programme aims to control tobacco-related oral diseases and adverse conditions through several strategies.

Within WHO, the Programme forms part of the WHO tobacco-free initiatives, with fully integrated oral health-related programmes.

Externally, the Programme encourages the adoption and use of WHO tobacco-cessation and control policies by international and national oral health organizations

**The Central Govt of India declared
31 MAY WORLD NO TOBACCO DAY**

World No - Tobacco Day

31 May

**UNITED
FOR A TOBACCO
FREE WORLD**

TOBACCO KILLS

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